

Conference Report

«Acting Together for Sustainable Scholar-Led Publishing» – 1st Swiss Diamond Open Access Conference

Daniela Hahn, Victoria Landau (PLATO)

What role does Diamond Open Access play in Switzerland and how can more awareness be raised for scholar-led publishing? What are the pathways to make Diamond Open Access publishing more sustainable? These questions served as the starting points for the 1st Swiss Diamond Open Access conference which took place on 8 March 2024 at the PROGR in Bern.

The conference was organised by the “Platinum Open Access Funding” project ([PLATO](#)) and featured contributions by international Diamond Open Access experts, representatives of hosting and funding institutions, learned societies, as well as editors of Diamond Open Access journals. Issues of sustainability stood at the centre of the discussions, particularly regarding funding but also regarding technical sustainability, interoperability, scientific quality assurance and enhanced collaboration with European projects dedicated to Diamond Open Access such as [CRAFT-OA](#) and [DIAMAS](#).

Rudolf Mumenthaler ([University Library Zurich](#)) and **Andrea Malits** ([Open Science Services, University Library Zurich](#)) kicked off the morning talks with “**PLATO: Furthering Diamond Open Access in Switzerland**”. The first part of their contribution highlighted the achievements of the PLATO project since its start in 2022: First, it has provided insights into the heterogeneous and multilingual Diamond Open Access landscape in

Switzerland by conducting a [study](#) on scholar-led journals, their workflows, challenges, and opportunities. Secondly, the project has also been able to raise more awareness for Diamond Open Access in Switzerland, which not only led to the inclusion of Diamond Open Access in the [Swiss Open Access Journal Monitor](#) (currently with a 3.7% share), but also to taking first steps towards the creation of a Diamond OA network of institutions and journal editors. By introducing a personal case study of the journal [Informations-praxis](#), which he co-founded in 2014, Rudolf Mumenthaler did stress the enthusiasm and dedication that editors put into community-led journals while also pointing out the challenges that these journals are facing. Due to a lack of succession planning and decreasing numbers of submissions, the journal had to cease its operation in 2024.

In the second part of the contribution, Andrea Malits focused on the exploration of funding models for Diamond Open Access and possible pathways for their implementation. For this implementation to be successful, she argued that “Swissness” has to be taken into account, meaning the highly decentralised system with federal and cantonal universities as well as the specific mandates for funding organisations and scholarly academies, which are not comparable with similar institutions abroad. Against this background, she presented four pledges regarding the enhancement of Diamond Open Access in Switzerland: (1) that costs should not be borne by universities alone, (2) that working with experienced service providers/publishers needs to be taken into consideration, (3) that research communities have to be involved to build trustworthiness and ensure scientific quality, and (4) that a national approach with a focus on learned societies seems promising and should be explored.

For the first keynote of the day, “**Sustaining Diamond Open Access. What We Know so Far**”, **Vanessa Proudman** ([SPARC Europe/SCOSS](#)) outlined some conclusions from the [January 2024 DIAMAS project survey](#) on the institutional publishing landscape. This included pinpointing areas in which collaboration across IPSPs and especially across national borders would be welcomed, and the main challenges posing obstacles: the lack of financial resources, precarious employment, and a dependence on parent organisations (more than half of all Diamond Open Access publishers rely on permanent funding by such entities). Stressing the need for common infrastructures, creating new models (and even legislation) to allow cross-border collaboration in a digital world and moving from time-limited grants to long-term public or government funding, the talk offered an outlook towards the DIAMAS [IPSP Sustainability Research Report](#), which was published in April 2024.

With “**Towards a European Capacity Hub and a Global Federation for Diamond Open Access**”, **Pierre Mounier** ([OPERAS/DIAMAS](#)) proposed a new governance structure for Diamond Open Access. Based on the speaker’s [December 2023 discussion paper](#), co-authored with Johan Rooryck, this four-level structure would be composed of communities (journals, scholarly communities), capacity centres (tools and service providers for journals), capacity hubs (capacity centre coordination at a regional/continental level) and a global federation (advocacy worldwide). A central reason given for the establishment of such a federated support architecture was the need for alignment, coordination and collaboration within the existing decentralised Diamond Open Access

landscape, which could be promoted and professionalised through this type of governance. As a final example, the talk focused on the work-in-progress of CRAFT-OA and DIAMAS, which would provide the necessary building blocks for developing a European Diamond capacity hub. Offering a step-by-step guidance for the improvement of individual capacity centres, this process would fulfil the necessary precondition for long-term sustainability of Diamond Open Access.

Rounding out the keynote section of the conference, **Dirk Verdicchio** ([Open Science, University Library of Bern](#)) elaborated on the role of libraries as publishing service providers (IPSP) in “**Building a Diamond Open Access Environment**”. Drawing on 12 years of experience at [Bern Open Publishing](#) (BOP) as well as a series of interviews conducted with editors of journals hosted by BOP, the talk shared observations on the diversity of intents behind the formation of a journal, the factors affecting the starting phase of journals (national or institutional factors, integrating publishing activities into wider policies or strategies, as well as the availability of funding), and the differing aims of journals. While some journals prefer a sense of ownership and autonomy by operating without the support of service providers, the talk concluded by highlighting the responsibility of IPSPs to convince journal editors of the usefulness of adhering to standards, making them better eligible for funding and more attractive for authors, as well as ensuring the proper implementation of requirements. Pointing to the upcoming revised [Swiss National Open Access Strategy](#), he expressed the hope that the efforts of many of the projects featured throughout the conference would make important contributions in the enhancement of Diamond Open Access publications and infrastructures in Switzerland.

The roundtable “**Initiatives for a Sustainable Future of Scholarly Communication**”, chaired by **Marc Thommen** ([University of Zurich](#)), opened with introductory statements by the four panellists.

In his statement, **Christian Schwarzenegger** ([swissuniversities](#)) stressed the achievements of the open access transformation in Switzerland since the National Open Access Strategy came into effect in 2017. By referring to the revised National Open Access Strategy which will be adopted this summer, he emphasised the role of Diamond Open Access publishing in achieving the goal of 100% open access in Switzerland while also conceding the fact that the Swiss scholarly communication system is still (and will be for the foreseeable future) highly dependent on commercial publishers due to the fact that Swiss higher education institutions find themselves in an international, competitive environment.

Jeannette Frey ([Consortium of Swiss Academic Libraries](#)) outlined a pathway to further Diamond Open Access by, first, stressing the importance of the scholarly communities that stand behind each scholar-led journal and that are often scattered around the globe. In order to support these community-led journals, in a second step, permanent, not project-mode funding would be required which, in turn, requires institutional missions as long-term commitments to the cause of Diamond Open Access.

In a similar vein, **Beat Immenhauser** ([Swiss Academy of Humanities and Social Sciences/SAGW](#)) stressed that the promotion of Diamond Open Access will not be possible without its recognition of Diamond Open Access as a standard in academic publishing and without the provision of adequate funding. Currently, the SAGW funds 75 journals, half of which are Diamond Open Access. As he pointed out, this funding, however, is not scalable since the SAGW can only support journals associated with learned societies. At the same time, he mentioned that, in line with the revised National Open Access Strategy, there are ideas of setting up a (temporary) Diamond Open Access fund which could spur the development of long-term funding options in the future.

Speaking on behalf of the [Open Access Working Group \(AKOA\)](#) of University Libraries, **Valérie Andres** addressed the lack of resources and expertise in libraries, which used to be experts in reading access rather than publishing. In order to enable libraries to play a significant role in open access publishing processes, she argued that libraries, on the one hand, require the support of the leaders of their institutions and, on the other hand, also need to strengthen their connections with researchers and research communities regarding their discipline-specific needs.

The conference concluded with a panel discussion on “**Diamond Open Access Practices: Quality, Efficiency and Sustainability**”, chaired by **Jean-Blaise Claivaz** ([Bibliothèque Université de Genève](#)), which focused on practical aspects of Diamond OA publishing through the lens of two journal editors and two representatives of IPSPs.

Introducing the services of [Bern Open Publishing \(BOP\)](#), which currently hosts 21 journals and four books, **Elio Pellin** (University Library Bern) not only detailed the support and advantages that BOP offers for editors (e.g. improved OJS workflows, long-term archiving, indexing, print on demand) but also highlighted the constant effort of the library team to improve services and enhance technical sustainability. For this to be achieved, he emphasised the importance of collaborating with European projects such as DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA (in which the University of Bern is a project partner) regarding information, training, guidelines, technical improvement, the simplification of installation and update procedures, platform interoperability, and the creation of a Diamond discovery hub.

As the manager of a second IPSP, [HOPE \(Hauptbibliothek Open Publishing Environment\)](#), the OJS-based journal publishing platform of the University of Zurich which currently hosts 19 journals, **Margit Dellatorre** also spoke to the platform’s objective of improving technical support for editors (e.g. by developing OJS plugins in-house) and potentially offering more services to editors in the future. In this context, she stressed the importance of trust between journal editors and service providers and the need to tailor services to the requirements of researchers in order to fill infrastructures with life. Technical sustainability and expanding service portfolios, however, would require investments in infrastructures and services which in the current climate of budget cuts to universities seem rather unlikely.

Based on the learnings from the history of editing and publishing the born-digital journal [Medienpädagogik](#), **Klaus Rummler** (PHZH) retraced the founding process of a new publishing cooperative that serves as a legal entity, therefore allowing “buy-ins” from institutions to support the Diamond Open Access journals that are part of this cooperative. Regarding the question of what is needed in order to enhance Diamond Open Access in Switzerland, he proposed the creation of a Swiss Knowledge Hub on Diamond Open Access and suggested that 10% of all article processing charges (APCs) spent in Switzerland could go to a Diamond Open Access fund. Furthermore, he argued that so-called “alternative deals” could be set up to allow libraries to engage in funding for scholar-led infrastructures instead of participating in expensive “transformative deals”.

From the double-perspective as a researcher and as president of [Swiss Medical Weekly Supporting Association](#), **Manuel Battegay** addressed the processes of quality assurance and sustainable funding as challenges for Diamond Open Access journals. Although the long publishing history of Swiss Medical Weekly and its backing by hospitals were important factors for the journal’s success, he emphasised the high degree of professionalism, the speed of publication, the robustness and sustainability of quality assurance procedures as well as the ability to adapt to changing circumstances as the foundations of its ongoing relevance. The competitiveness of the publishing market, particularly in the life sciences, he conceded, would require some form of competitive funding opportunities for Diamond Open Access journals whilst also securing the basic operations of publishing infrastructures.

In bringing together the Swiss Diamond Open Access community, the conference provided an opportunity for exchange, networking and for discussing different, at times even diverging views regarding Diamond Open Access in Switzerland. These discussions made it clear that the securing of funding for Diamond Open Access publishing is tied to two dimensions: On the one hand, it requires the recognition of Diamond Open Access as a high-quality publishing option by the research communities and the reform of research assessment with a focus on quality rather than “brand”. At the same time, it also depends on the willingness of institutions to support Diamond Open Access and to realise their responsibility of adopting Diamond Open Access as part of their mission. For this, the conference succeeded in offering some concrete ideas for a roadmap towards furthering Diamond Open Access in collaboration with European projects and initiatives. Many speakers were looking forward to future editions of this conference, speaking to the need for these types of forums in the field.

Programme

10h00

Welcome

Daniela Hahn (PLATO)

10h15

“PLATO: Furthering Diamond Open Access in Switzerland”

Rudolf Mumenthaler (Director University Library Zurich)

Andrea Malits (Lead Open Science Services, University Library Zurich)

10h45

Coffee Break

11h00

Keynotes: Sustainability and Collaboration

“Sustaining Diamond Open Access. What We Know so Far”

Vanessa Proudman (SPARC Europe/SCOSS)

“Towards a European Capacity Hub and a Global Federation for Diamond Open Access”

Pierre Mounier (OPERAS/DIAMAS)

“Building a Diamond Open Access Environment”

Dirk Verdicchio (Head Open Science, University Library Bern)

12h30

Lunch Break

13h30

Roundtable: Initiatives for a Sustainable Future of Scholarly Communication

Chair: Marc Thommen (University of Zurich)

- Valérie Andres (FHNW Library/Co-President AKOA)
- Jeannette Frey (Bibliothèque Cantonale et Universitaire Lausanne/Consortium of Swiss Academic Libraries)
- Beat Immenhauser (Swiss Academy of Humanities and Social Sciences)
- Christian Schwarzenegger (swissuniversities)

15h00

Coffee Break

15h30

Diamond Open Access Practices: Quality, Efficiency and Sustainability

Moderation: Jean-Blaise Claivaz (Bibliothèque Université de Genève)

- Manuel Battegay (*Swiss Medical Weekly*)
- Margit Dellatorre (University Library Zurich/HOPE)
- Elio Pellin (University Library Bern/CRAFT OA)
- Klaus Rummeler (PHZH/*MedienPädagogik. Zeitschrift für Theorie und Praxis der Medienbildung*)

17h00

Wrap Up

